

Voltage stability in the WSCC power system for large-scale integration of renewable energy

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Abstract. The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) introduces significant challenges to the stability of the electrical grid, particularly in maintaining voltage stability, due to the unpredictable nature of these sources. This unpredictability can impact the overall security and reliability of the system. Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) enhance this stability by managing the flow of active and reactive power, which is crucial in systems such as the WSCC. The widely studied 9-bus system serves as scenario for the contingency analysis, loadability analysis and sensitivity analysis. All these are made with the objective to assess the improvements of large-scale RES integration into the grid.

Keywords: renewable energy, RES, FACTS, voltage stability.

1 Introduction

The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into the electrical grid presents significant stability challenges, particularly concerning voltage stability. This is primarily due to their unpredictable and intermittent nature, which can greatly affect the overall security and reliability of the power system [1]. As these renewable sources, such as wind and solar power, depend on climatic conditions, their variability introduces uncertainty in power generation, making grid management more complex.

To address these challenges, Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) play a vital role in enhancing grid stability [2]. FACTS devices help control and manage the flow of active and reactive power within the grid, thus maintaining a balanced and stable system. This capability is crucial for ensuring that power can be efficiently distributed and consumed, especially in complex grid systems like the Western System Coordinating Council (WSCC).

The WSCC, a prominent system referenced in many studies, includes a well-known 9-bus model that serves as a common scenario for conducting various types of analyses. In this context, contingency analysis is used to assess the system's response to unexpected failures or changes, loadability analysis examines the maximum load the system

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can handle before becoming unstable, and sensitivity analysis helps identify how changes in system parameters can affect system behavior. Together, these analyses provide a comprehensive understanding of the system's dynamics and resilience.

This work analyses the injection of large-scale renewable energy into the WSCC system to demonstrate it can improve the voltage stability of the system in different scenarios. Specifically, a wind farm comprised of doubly fed induction generators (DFIG). These are type 3 wind turbines (WT), according to the classification of the international electrotechnical commission (IEC).

2 Methodology

The methodology chosen for assessing voltage stability in the WSCC system begins with conducting a standard power flow analysis under normal conditions using the Electrical Transient and Analysis Program (ETAP). The results obtained from ETAP are then compared with those found in authoritative textbooks to ensure accuracy and consistency [3]. For added validation, the power flow analysis is also executed using the PSAT toolbox [4], showing results that align closely with those reported in the literature. It's important to note that these validation processes underscore the reliability of the software tools used in the analysis. In Fig. 1 the object of study is presented.

Fig. 1. The WSCC 9 bus 3 generator system in ETAP. Notice the voltages and phase angles calculated very similar to those published in [3].

A notable aspect of this analysis is the difference in how each software program inputs the system parameters. For instance, ETAP requires system impedance input in ohms per kilometer, whereas PSAT uses the per unit (p.u.) total to define transmission line impedances. These discrepancies necessitate careful unit conversion and parameter

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adjustment, which inherently contribute to the small variations observed in numerical results from the power flow analysis.

Following the initial power flow analysis, the WSCC system undergoes contingency analysis. This involves systematically disconnecting each transmission line and analyzing the resulting power flow scenarios to identify the bus with the lowest voltage, if it is below 90% of the nominal voltage for more than one minute, this is known as an undervoltage condition. Each scenario derived from the contingency analysis is then further examined through active power versus voltage (P-V) curves, reactive power versus voltage (Q-V) curves, and voltage versus reactive power (V-Q) sensitivity analyses to understand the system's robustness and identify potential vulnerabilities.

In contingency scenarios—with transmission lines being selectively removed—the power flow calculations reveal which bus bar experiences the lowest voltage. This assessment helps simulate an incident where existing loads must be supplied through alternative pathways within the system. Along with the normal operation scenario of the WSCC system (with no contingencies), these seven scenarios are analyzed using P-V curves, also referred to as Nose-curves. P-V curves are instrumental in evaluating the loadability of each bus bar, providing insights into how much more load each bus bar can handle before reaching instability [5].

Additionally, Q-V curve analyses are conducted for each scenario, focusing on the sensitivity of bus voltages to changes in reactive power injection. Q-V curves are crucial for utilities as they gauge proximity to voltage collapse, enabling operators to make informed decisions to maintain system stability. These analyses illustrate the maximum reactive power that can be supported by the most vulnerable bus before voltage levels drop to critical limits, thus averting potential instability [6].

The V-Q sensitivity analysis, specifically within the ETAP software, ranks each bus by assessing voltage sensitivity as adjustments are made to reactive power in the system. This ranking provides valuable insight into which buses are most susceptible to voltage changes, allowing operators and planners to implement strategies that maintain optimal system performance and avert possible disruptions in the event of power fluctuations or unexpected contingencies [7].

These analyses are also done for the seven contingency scenarios but with the inclusion of large-scale renewable energy with the aim of improving the voltage stability in the most vulnerable bus bar. As mentioned in the introduction the equivalent/aggregate model [8] of the wind farm is one DFIG WT of 70 MW nominal power with a static VAR compensator (SVC) at the wind farm common bus before the step-up transformer. The windfarm is modeled with an aggregated model as in [9] and [10].

3 Results and discussions

In Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the numerical results from the power flow for each scenario are presented. The lowest bus voltage and the largest phase angle are highlighted with a yellow background for each scenario. The lowest bus voltage of all scenarios is shown in red, while the second lowest is shown in orange.

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Note the similarities in the original scenario for both software programs. This, combined with the results presented in [3], confirms the accuracy and consistency of the calculations in both software programs. However, PSAT calculates an even worse undervoltage condition for the scenario without the transmission line between bus 4 and bus 5, marked in red.

Removal of the transmission line between the bus bars x-y	ETAP												Original	
	5-7		6-9		7-8		8-9		4-6		4-5		Voltage (pu)	Phase (deg)
	Voltage (pu)	Phase (deg)												
Bus 1	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0
Bus 2	1.025	31.67	1.025	18.83	1.025	20.55	1.025	7.36	1.025	6.59	1.025	6.05	1.025	9.3
Bus 3	1.025	18.5	1.025	20.14	1.025	-5.4	1.025	8.42	1.025	-0.125	1.025	2.94	1.025	4.68
Bus 4	0.9999	-1.91	1.007	-1.92	1.017	-2	1.023	-1.98	1.028	-1.93	1.038	-1.5	1.026	-2.21
Bus 5	0.9497	-7.51	0.9716	-0.514	0.9765	-0.01	0.9906	-4.53	0.9981	-4.72	0.9021	-9.23	0.9957	-3.97
Bus 6	0.9794	1.39	0.9712	-6.18	1.03	-7.08	1.009	-2.21	0.9602	-10.67	1.02	-3.84	1.013	-3.67
Bus 7	1.018	26.06	1.017	13.22	1.02	14.96	1.012	1.73	1.024	1.02	1.004	0.37	1.026	3.74
Bus 8	1.002	19.51	1.007	12.72	0.9777	-13.38	0.9831	-2.03	1.01	-2.85	1.002	-1.94	1.016	0.747
Bus 9	1.02	15.77	1.024	17.42	1.016	-8.14	1.034	5.72	1.021	-2.85	1.029	0.238	1.032	1.98

Fig. 2. Results from the Power Flow analysis in ETAP for each of the seven scenarios.

Removal of the transmission line between the bus bars x-y	PSAT												Original	
	5-7		6-9		7-8		8-9		4-6		4-5		Voltage (pu)	Phase (deg)
	Voltage (pu)	Phase (deg)												
Bus 1	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0	1.04	0
Bus 2	1.025	30.2256	1.025	17.8218	1.025	19.8879	1.025	6.1479	1.025	4.7212	1.025	-1.4531	1.025	9.28
Bus 3	1.025	17.1931	1.025	19.0452	1.025	-7.1631	1.025	8.1165	1.025	-3.0209	1.025	-1.9869	1.025	4.6648
Bus 4	0.99559	-2.5574	1.0047	-2.4166	1.0159	-2.4713	1.0225	-2.2462	1.0282	-2.2578	1.0388	-2.3397	1.0258	-2.2168
Bus 5	0.93801	-8.8294	0.96779	-1.3923	0.97363	-0.71008	0.98969	-5.1713	0.99881	-5.5664	0.83875	-20.394	0.99563	-3.9888
Bus 6	0.97481	0.30975	0.96387	-7.0928	0.99938	-8.077	1.0087	-2.5078	0.94182	-14.621	1.0203	-6.0661	1.0127	-3.6874
Bus 7	1.017	24.6174	1.0157	12.2059	1.0192	14.2915	1.01	0.5004	1.0223	-0.85828	0.98772	-7.2283	1.0258	3.7197
Bus 8	1.001	18.0586	1.0054	11.6249	0.96904	-15.6343	0.97828	-3.5408	1.0063	-5.1948	0.98948	-8.5309	1.0159	0.72753
Bus 9	1.0189	14.4594	1.0234	16.3236	1.0126	-9.9139	1.0338	5.4223	1.0167	-5.7605	1.0244	-4.7059	1.0324	1.9667

Fig. 3. Results from the Power Flow analysis in PSAT for each of the seven scenarios.

It is safe to say that the contingency involving the transmission line between bus 4 and bus 5 represents the worst scenario for undervoltage at busbar number 5. In Fig. 4, the P-V curve for the three buses with loads in the WSCC system under a contingency between bus 4 and bus 5 is shown. The loadability of bus 5 is compromised since the nominal load of the bus 5 is 125 MW according to [3]. This indicates a deficit of active power, meaning that additional sources should be added to overcome the undervoltage.

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Fig. 4. P-V curves for the three buses with loads in the WSCC without the transmission line between bus 4 and 5.

In Fig. 5 the Q-V curve for the three buses with loads in WSCC system under a contingency between bus 4 and 5. From Fig. 5 is evident the high sensitivity of bus 5.

Fig. 5. Q-V curves for the three buses with loads in the WSCC without the transmission line between bus 4 and 5.

In Fig. 6, the sensitivity analysis of the worst contingency scenario is presented. Here, the sensitivity of bus 5 to changes in reactive power is much higher than that of any other bus once the transmission line between bus 4 and bus 5 is removed. Please bear in mind that this study concerns a sustained interruption, meaning one that lasts longer than one minute according to standards (e.g., IEEE-1159, ANSI-C84.1). The goal of any grid operator should be to prevent voltage collapse due to possible load variations. Since the load at bus 5 can vary throughout the day, a sufficient loadability

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margin should be maintained for active and reactive power demand at bus 5, even when the transmission line is absent, to prevent voltage collapse. This situation strongly supports the argument for adding RES at bus 5.

Fig. 6. V-Q sensitivity analysis without the transmission line between bus 4 and 5.

3.1 The addition of RES

This section examines the analysis of bus 5 with the injection of RES. Here the RES is a 70 MW Type 3 wind farm equipped with a Static Var Compensator (SVC) as detailed in the introduction. The SVC can provide a 45 MVar injection at bus 5. Figure 7 illustrates the WSCC system with the RES injection at bus 5. Notably, the SVC is connected to the common coupling bus of the wind farm, positioned before the step-up transformer.

Fig. 7. The WSCC 9 bus system with the addition of RES in bus 5 (red rectangle).

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3.2 Improvements in voltage stability

Figure 8 illustrates the analysis of the worst contingency scenario now incorporating RES. Notably, the bus voltage remains stable, not dropping below 5%, primarily due to the integration of the wind farm. Additionally, the overall system voltage shows improvement with the addition of RES. Figure 9 presents the P-V curves for the three buses with loads in the WSCC, including RES at bus 5. Here, one can observe the enhanced loadability of the bus and the avoidance of an undervoltage condition at bus 5. This demonstrates that, even during the contingency, the loads at bus 5 can be adequately supplied without resorting to extreme measures such as undervoltage load shedding. It is noteworthy that the load at bus 5 is 125 MW, which, as shown in Fig. 9, is well above the 5% lower voltage threshold, with ample margin from the point of voltage collapse (PoVC) on the nose curve.

Figure 10 displays the Q-V curves for the buses with loads in the WSCC system, factoring in RES and the contingency between bus 4 and bus 5. In comparison to Fig. 5, the Q-V curve in Fig. 10 for bus 5 shows significant improvement. This indicates that, even under contingency conditions, the reactive power consumption at bus 5 can be increased by more than 50% without reducing the bus voltage below 95% of its nominal value.

These analyses clearly indicate an improvement in both loadability and reactive power sensitivity at the bus experiencing the lowest voltage during the studied contingencies. It is essential to highlight that, although the wind farm is modeled as an aggregated entity, the ETAP software incorporates wind turbine models that remain effective even under transient conditions. This insight underscores the capabilities of the simulation software to model and optimize the performance of renewable energy systems in dynamic grid situations, enhancing overall grid resilience and stability.

Fig. 8. The WSCC 9 bus system with RES at bus 5 during the contingency between bus 4 and 5.

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Fig. 9. P-V curves for the three buses with loads in the WSCC without the transmission line between bus 4 and 5 and with 70 MW of RES addition in bus 5. Dotted line is without RES.

Another important detail of the wind farm model is the inclusion of the SVC. This is a common arrangement in onshore wind farms as reported in previous literature[11, 12].

Fig. 10. Q-V curves for the three buses with loads in the WSCC without the transmission line between bus 4 and 5. Dotted line is without RES.

In Fig. 11 the contingency between bus 5 and 4 is shown for the scenario where the wind farm is connected to the bus 6 instead of the bus 5. Here is visible that the undervoltage condition in bus 5 occurs even though the injection of RES. It is important to mention that this study was carried out for the RES in bus 8 with similar results, see Fig. 12. In Fig. 11 and Fig.12 the red rectangle indicates the 70 MW type 3 wind farm.

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Fig. 11. WSCC with RES in bus 6 during the contingency in between bus 5 and 4.

Fig. 12. WSCC with RES in bus 6 during the contingency in between bus 5 and 4.

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4 Conclusions

From the analyses presented in the last section, some important conclusions can be drawn. First, the contingency analysis shows that the worst-case scenario is the removal of the transmission line between buses 4 and 5. This contingency causes an undervoltage condition on bus 5, which could lead to a voltage collapse of the grid, as the bus P-V curve during the contingency demonstrates reduced loadability and increased sensitivity in the Q-V curve.

Second, the addition of renewable energy sources (RES) at the bus with the lowest voltage during the contingency alleviates the undervoltage condition and improves loadability and reactive power supply. This improvement is contingent upon the wind farm being adequately equipped with a Static Var Compensator (SVC), as is common with many modern wind farms.

Third, the point of coupling for the RES in the power system should be carefully studied to enhance voltage stability. Not every location for RES injection can effectively alleviate the undervoltage condition during a contingency. Therefore, studies like the one presented here should be conducted and considered during the planning of grid growth and expansion.

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